

Figure 1: Motorcycles “driving in the corridor” in a typical Brazilian traffic scenario. © Alf Ribeiro

Rota 2030:

Motorcycle Detection in the Vehicle Blind Spot Using a Radar Sensor

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Figure 2: Bounding box generated by the RSS model, which determines a critical area. © Facens

Nowadays, series-produced vehicles are equipped with advanced driver assistance systems responsible for helping the driver in order to promote more comfort and safety. The use of these systems is becoming increasingly common in developed countries. In Europe the European Parliament has made some of these systems mandatory in the production of vehicles from May 2022 – such as the automatic emergency braking.¹ However, vehicles equipped with these features may have different reactions when operating in Brazil, since Brazilian traffic scenarios are different from other countries due to different traffic laws, habits, and driving patterns, especially concerning the heavy motorcycles traffic on urban roads. Based on this, the multinationals Robert Bosch Ltda. and Fiat Chrysler Automobiles (Stellantis) together with the Facens University, the Aeronautics Institute of Technology, and the Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt have joined forces in an applied research project in the area of vehicle safety, aiming to develop a system using radar sensors installed in cars – capable of detecting motorcycles in blind spots “driving in the corridors” of Brazilian urban roads, as shown in Fig 1.

This project is funded by the Rota 2030 – a new Brazilian funding program that offers tax incentives to the automotive industry to invest in technological developments and innovations and in joint R&D projects with universities. The project named “Detecting motorcycles in the vehicles’ blind spot using radar sensors” was approved with the highest score in its funding line and with a total volume of approximately 260,000 euros, of which 155,000 euros are directly funded by the Brazilian Ministry of Economy and 105,000 euros correspond to the co-funding jointly invested by all partners. The experiments of the project are carried out both with the help of simulation and real tests with motorcycles and test vehicles in Brazil and on proving grounds in Germany (CARISSMA Institute of Automated Driving). Simulated and real tests complement each other in order to achieve academic and applied results which will be possibly implemented in the motorcycles detection system in cars developed in the Brazilian automotive industry.

What is the challenge in Brazilian traffic? A notable characteristic of Brazilian traffic scenarios is the presence of motorcycles driving in a usually aggressive manner between vehicles while lane splitting. In Brazil, this practice is known as “driving in the corridor”, which is formed between two traffic lanes, and is already ingrained in the culture of Brazilian motorcyclists, who seek to reduce travel time by taking advantage of a possible gap between vehicles, often with minimal space for such. For those who have never been to Brazil, it may not be so easy to imagine this scenario and its consequences. However, these practices can lead to serious accidents. While motorcycles are driving in the corridors, vehicles that are changing lanes frequently collide with motorcyclists. This fact was verified by a survey conducted in 2018 by the Ministry of Transport, Ports, and Aviation, in Brazil, which shows that 53.7% of traffic accidents are caused by driver recklessness, with 30.3% disrespecting traffic laws and 23.4% due to driver inattention.² Furthermore, according to the official Brazilian information systems

on mortality and hospitalisation, 2,492 out of a total of 28,995 (8.6%) road deaths were motorcyclists in the year 2000. This number increased dramatically 18 years later when 11,479 motorcyclist fatalities occurred out of total of 32,655 (32.7%) road deaths.³ Although, driving in the corridors is allowed in accordance with the Brazilian traffic law⁴ and drivers have a great responsibility in maintaining traffic safety.

How is the project developed and how is it helping to solve this problem? The project's initial approach consists of cataloguing critical traffic scenarios involving motorcycles in the corridor based on reports of accidents that have occurred in the city of Campinas, in the state of São Paulo, Brazil. The goal is to understand the conjuncture of these accidents and to collect information describing the main locations and types of accidents that occur on urban roads. In this way, it is possible to recreate the scenarios and events that preceded these accidents up to the moment of impact in automotive simulation software, such as, for example, CARLA Simulator.⁵ The use of simulation allows us to understand from which moment a scenario becomes critical based on the detection results of other vehicles and vehicle dynamics parameters (among others longitudinal and lateral speed, distance between vehicles and driver reaction time). This analysis is based on Responsibility-Sensitive Safety (RSS), a mathematical model developed by Mobileye, which formalizes human notions of safe driving using a set of mathematical formulas and logical rules that are transparent and verifiable.⁶ This model also allows estimating, in real-time, the criticality of a current scenario using radar sensor information combined with vehicle information, as shown in Fig 2.

In the simulation, the outcome of scenario criticality depends on the quality of the radar sensor models implemented, as these can describe a motorcycle even too ideally or unrealistically compared to motorcycle measurements with real sensors. To establish a new state of the art of radar sensor modelling, the project aims to develop a radar model based on Artificial Intelligence using generative models. This enables the generation of radar signatures of motorcycles as realistic as possible with the help of simulation. The radar signature of an object can be described by the Radar Cross Section (RCS) which measures the intensity with which an object can reflect electromagnetic waves. For example, a person has an RCS of approximately 1dBsm, while a motorcycle has an RCS between 10 and 15 dBsm and trucks around 30 dBsm.⁷ In other words, the larger the surface area of a target and the greater the ability of its materials to reflect electromagnetic waves, the greater its RCS. Since the RCS values differ for different types of vehicles, this information is essential for the detection of a motorcycle in the blind

Figure 3: Left: Real motorcycle with measured RCS values. Right: Virtual motorcycle with simulated RCS values. © Facens

spot and its differentiation from other vehicles and objects. The characterization of real motorcycles is done in the scope of this project, as shown in Fig 3, by performing real tests. Similarly, the characterization of the virtual motorcycle occurs by creating a 3D model from a real motorcycle, also shown in Fig 3, using raytracing-based algorithms to generate RCS values consistent with reality. The results are used to develop detection and tracking algorithms for motorcycles in radar measurements using real and synthetically generated data.

Besides this characterization, the project is about estimating the limits of detection of a motorcycle by a Bosch radar sensor installed in a car in different situations. It is necessary to understand in which scenarios the sensor is efficient to detect motorcycles in the corridor and when its performance starts to degrade according to the complexity of the situation, such as the presence of noise from other detected vehicles and the separability of the motorcycle from clutter. Then, knowing how a motorcycle can be properly measured by radar, it is possible to develop algorithms for motorcycle detection and tracking. These algorithms are necessary to measure their distance and speed based on data acquired in an instant of time, when a motorcycle is detected by the sensor. They also can estimate these values precisely, when it is briefly in an undetectable area. In this way, it is possible to keep the driver constantly aware of his/her surroundings in an appropriate manner so that an accident can be avoided. The partners will integrate the results achieved over 2 years of intensive research – from early 2021 to end 2022 – and demonstrate it in the form of a prototype: a driver alert system integrated into a test vehicle, both in software and hardware. This system will be validated by the Brazilian automotive industry from 2023. The result is a promising road safety system that is being developed specifically for the Brazilian traffic scenario but could potentially be adapted to other countries with similar motorcycle traffic in urban roads. This project incorporates international research and development know-how in various areas that are explored innovatively in a partnership between major companies and university research in Brazil and Germany.

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